

THE EFFECT OF A POST-CONSOLIDATION HEAT TREATMENT ON THE TENSILE AND CREEP BEHAVIOR OF NEAT Ti-22Al-23Nb

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ABSTRACT

A study has been conducted to examine the effect of post-consolidation heat treatment on the longitudinal tensile and creep properties of an orthorhombic-based titanium aluminide, Ti-22Al-23Nb(a%), in neat matrix form. Heat treatment parameters were selected such that they would be consistent with future inclusion into the consolidation cycle for the fabrication of continuously-reinforced orthorhombic titanium matrix composites (O TMC's). The effects of heat treatment on microstructural evolution including type and morphology of the phase constituents was examined via secondary scanning electron microscopy and quantitative image analysis. Variations in microstructural features were correlated with resulting room temperature tensile properties (UTS, YS, %El and modulus), as well as, with isothermal creep response at 650°C/172MPa.

INTRODUCTION

Titanium aluminide composites based upon Ti₃Al (alpha-2, hexagonal DO₁₉ structure) have been the subject of numerous investigations in recent years (1,2). The majority of these studies have focused on a SiC reinforced Ti-24Al-11Nb (at%) matrix alloy as representative of this class of materials. The deficiencies associated with this alloy as a matrix for compositing have been well documented, and include: poor fiber/matrix reactivity, modest low and elevated temperature tensile strength, low fracture resistance, poor creep response and high sensitivity to interstitial embrittlement (3,4). Recent studies have begun to focus on an alternative titanium aluminide matrix alloy based upon the orthorhombic (Ti₂AlNb) phase (5). Results (6,7) from studies involving the orthorhombic composition, Ti-22Al-23Nb seem to suggest that this matrix class offers the following benefits relative to Ti-24Al-11Nb: reduced fiber/matrix reactivity, improved fracture resistance, increased tensile strength and increased resistance to elevated temperature creep deformation. Unfortunately, the creep response obtained even for the Ti-22Al-23Nb alloy in its as-fabricated form, still falls short of that required for advanced propulsion applications currently under consideration. Therefore, the objective of the subject study is to utilize a post-consolidation heat treatment as a means to modify the matrix microstructure of the Ti-22Al-23Nb alloy, so as to increase its tensile and creep performance.

EXPERIMENTAL

The neat Ti-22Al-23Nb matrix material utilized in the subject study was produced using a conventional ingot to foil reduction approach. Atlantic Research/IMT fabricated the neat matrix material by hot isostatic pressing (HIP'ing) five foils laid up in the same orientation with respect to the foil rolling direction. Longitudinally oriented rectangular specimens measuring

10mm (w) x 100 mm (l) x 0.1mm(t) were machined from the neat panels using low speed diamond cutting. Specimens were wrapped in tantalum and heat treated in vacuum (10^{-6} torr) after flushing with high purity argon.

All heat treatments were applied after consolidation of the neat matrix. The beta transus of Ti-22Al-23Nb neat material had previously been determined to be approximately 1100°C . A total of four solution heat treatment temperatures were examined: three subtransus (1025°C , 1050°C and 1075°C) and one supertransus (1125°C). In addition, two cooling rates (direct from the solution heat treatment temperature to the aging temperature) were evaluated: $28^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $2.8^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Finally, three aging schemes were studied: $760^{\circ}\text{C}/16\text{hr}$, $815^{\circ}\text{C}/8\text{hr}$ and $870^{\circ}\text{C}/4\text{hr}$. The baseline set of conditions selected for the study were: $1075^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{hr} + 28^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min} + 815^{\circ}\text{C}/8\text{hr}/\text{FC}$. The heat treatment conditions were selected such that they could be integrated into the composite fabrication cycle.

Microstructural analysis including determination of phase distribution, morphology and size was accomplished by secondary imaging of the as-fabricated and heat treated neat materials using a 360FE Leica SEM with a spatial resolution of 2nm at 25kV. Volume fraction determination of the constituent phases was accomplished using an image analysis program via a density slice function applied to stored digital backscattered SEM images. Microstructural characteristics were correlated with corresponding mechanical property levels.

Mechanical behavior examination included room temperature (23°C) tensile properties, as well as, elevated temperature isothermal creep ($650^{\circ}\text{C}/172\text{ MPa}$). A minimum of two tensile tests were conducted per heat treatment condition. Tensile tests were conducted under stroke-control at a constant crosshead speed of $0.0084\text{mm}/\text{s}$. Two creep tests were run per condition: 1) to 0.4% creep strain and 2) to at least 300 hours of creep life. All tests were conducted on a horizontal servo-hydraulic system. Details regarding the test system can be found elsewhere (8). Selected fractography was conducted on tensile specimens using secondary SEM imaging.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure

The as-fabricated neat microstructure is displayed in Figure 1. It is seen to contain three ordered phases, consistent with previous results for orthorhombic alloys of similar chemistry containing high levels of oxygen (9). The dark primary phase is alpha-2 (α_2) or Ti_3Al (hexagonal DO_{19} structure). This phase represents approximately 35v% of the structure, is fine-grained ($5\text{-}10\mu\text{m}$) and relatively equiaxed. The two phase mixture is a combination of orthorhombic "O" (light gray) platelets ($\sim 1\mu\text{m} \times 5\mu\text{m}$) in an ordered beta (B2) matrix (white). The "O" phase is based upon the Ti_2AlNb composition and represents a distortion of the α_2 structure by changing slightly the magnitude of the Burger's vectors of equivalent a and c+a dislocations in the α_2 structure. Note: Graves et al., (10) had previously determined that the beta phase was ordered for this composition. In addition, the perimeter of the primary α_2 phase is encased by a thin layer ($\sim 0.5\mu\text{m}$) of "O" phase, however, it has not been determined if this is the same variant as the "O" platelets formed from the B2 phase. Previous studies (5) have indicated that the "O" phase can form as a transformation product from the B2 phase after solution treatment during aging, or by a phase separation reaction within the α_2 phase (i.e. Nb segregates to the perimeter of the α_2). The corresponding volume fractions of the "O" and B2 phases were found to be 33v% and 30v%, respectively, with the B2 phase being continuous.

Figure 2 contains SEM micrographs showing the effects of solution heat treatment on microstructural response. In this instance the cooling rate and aging treatment conditions were held constant at $28^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $815^{\circ}\text{C}/8\text{hr}/\text{FC}$, respectively. It can be seen that the primary α_2 phase content decreases continually up through the 1075°C solution treatment, after which it is totally dissolved as the beta transus is exceeded at 1125°C . An inverse relationship was found for the "O" phase content in that it is seen to be continually increasing with increasing solution treatment temperature. The B2 phase content appears to be relatively unchanged, and thus, the increase in "O" appears associated with a corresponding decrease in α_2 .

Figure 1. As-fabricated neat microstructure containing three ordered phases: O, B2 and α_2

1025°C

1050°C

1075°C

1125°C

Figure 2. Effect of Solution Heat Treatment Temperature on Microstructure (Cooling Rate = 28°C/min; Age = 815°C/8hr/FC)

decrease in the α_2 phase. Previous studies (11) have indicated that the α_2 phase has poor ductility below $\sim 600^\circ\text{C}$ due to the anisotropy of slip associated with the DO_{19} structure. $\langle a \rangle$ Slip is seen to occur relatively easily on the prism plane, while $\langle c+a/2 \rangle$ slip is very difficult. As a result, large incompatibility stresses can build up at α_2/α_2 interfaces. As the solution heat treatment temperature increases, the number of α_2/α_2 interfaces decrease, and the surrounding B2 phase acts to accommodate these stresses. In addition, Banerjee (11) has demonstrated that the amount of $c+a$ slip available for the "O" phase is significantly more than for the α_2 phase.

Tensile Behavior

Table I contains the tensile properties corresponding to the solution heat treatment conditions previously discussed. In all instances the UTS, YS, %El and modulus have increased relative to the as-fabricated condition. The only exception to this being the ductility (elastic + plastic) after the 1125°C solution treatment. The 1050°C solution treatment appears to provide the best combination of UTS, %El and Modulus. It would appear that the increase in tensile properties is associated with an increase in the volume fraction of the "O" phase and a corresponding

Table I. Effect of Solution Heat Treatment Temperature on Tensile Properties

Condition	UTS(MPa)	YS(MPa)	%El	Modulus(GPa)
As-Fab'd	972	805	8.4	105
$1025^\circ\text{C}/2\text{hr}^*$	1096	848	9.0	119
$1050^\circ\text{C}/2\text{hr}^*$	1111	836	14.8	121
$1075^\circ\text{C}/2\text{hr}^*$	1059	810	11.5	120
$1125^\circ\text{C}/2\text{hr}$	1053	926	4.0	135

*Solution Heat Treatment + $28^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ + $815^\circ\text{C}/8\text{hr}/\text{FC}$

Having determined the effect of solution heat treatment temperature on tensile properties, the effects of cooling rate and aging treatment were independently examined. First, the effect of reducing the cooling rate by a factor of 10 from $28^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $2.8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ was evaluated by selecting a constant solution heat treatment of $1075^\circ\text{C}/2\text{hr}$ and a constant aging treatment of $815^\circ\text{C}/8\text{hr}/\text{FC}$. The results are contrasted (Table II) with the as-fabricated condition, and the baseline heat treatment, wherein the later the cooling rate was $28^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. It can be noticed that the UTS and YS both drop with respect to both the as-fabricated and baseline conditions, that the ductility is similar to the baseline heat treatment, and the modulus is intermediate to the two conditions. The decrease in strength is most likely associated with increased lath size of the "O" platelets and hence the mean free slip length across individual platelets. Previous studies by Koss et al (12) suggest that strength is inversely proportional to this mean slip length. In addition, the volume fraction of the lower strength α_2 phase has increased.

In a similar fashion, the effect of aging treatment was evaluated by again holding the solution treatment condition ($1075^\circ\text{C}/2\text{hr}$) and cooling rate ($28^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) constant, while examining two additional (beyond the baseline $815^\circ\text{C}/8\text{hr}$) aging treatments of $760^\circ\text{C}/16\text{hr}$ and $870^\circ\text{C}/4\text{hr}$. The results of the two aging treatments on tensile properties are also shown in Table II. The lower temperature age provides for a slight increase in UTS, and a relatively large increase in YS when compared to the as-fabricated and baseline heat treatment conditions. In addition, a significant decrease in ductility and an intermediate modulus value can be observed. These changes can be explained in terms of the resulting microstructure. It was noticed that the lower aging temperature resulted in a much finer O+B2 secondary structure, as well as, a semi-continuous layer of α_2 . The finer scale of the secondary structure gives rise to increased strength levels due to Hall-Petch boundary strengthening, while in conjunction with the semi-continuous nature of the α_2 , results in reduced ductility for reasons noted earlier. The higher temperature aging treatment results in UTS, YS and %EL values similar to that of the baseline heat treatment condition with an intermediate modulus value. It was observed that the resulting microstructure had changed relative to the 815°C age, in that the volume fraction of α_2 increased, but it remained discontinuous. In addition, the "O" lath size had increased, while the B2 phase remained continuous. The fracture morphology of the 760°C age was dominated by transgranular cleavage of both the "O" platelets and α_2 grains with little evidence of ductile dimpling. Conversely, the material when aged at 870°C displayed a fracture exhibiting a significant amount of ductile dimpling produced by microvoid coalescence of primarily the B2 phase, while transgranular fracture of the α_2 and "O" phases was still observed.

The overall results of the effect of heat treatment on tensile behavior would seem to suggest that the Ti-22Al-23Nb alloy is heat treatable to improved combinations of UTS, YS, %El and modulus compared to the as-fabricated neat matrix. Furthermore, if a combination of good strength and ductility are required, a heat treatment incorporating a high sub-transus (β -50°C) solution treatment followed by a rapid cool (28°C/min) and intermediate to high aging temperature (815-870°C) provide the best results.

Table II. Effect of Cooling Rate and Aging Treatment on Tensile Behavior

Condition	UTS(MPa)	YS(MPa)	%El	Modulus(GPa)
As-Fab'd	972	805	8.4	105
Baseline HT*	1059	810	11.5	120
2.8°C/min**	946	725	11.2	114
760°C/16hr/FC#	1098	931	5.5	109
870°C/4hr/FC#	1062	810	12.3	113

* 1075°C/2hr+28°C/min to 815°C/8hr/FC

**Sol'n HT = 1075°C/2hr; Age = 815°C/8hr/FC

Sol'n HT = 1075°C/2hr; Cooling Rate = 28°C/min

Creep Behavior

The effects of solution heat treatment on isothermal creep behavior at 650°C/172 MPa are shown in Table III. As previously noted two tests per condition were run: 1) to 0.4% total creep strain and 2) to 300 hours of creep life. Therefore, the times shown to 0.4% creep strain are the average of two data points, while the 300 hour rupture criterion represents a singular value. Also shown are the minimum creep rates and the time spent in the primary creep regime. It can be noticed as the solution heat treatment temperature increases, the time to 0.4% creep strain increases such that the super-transus treatment provides for an increase of >15x life extension compared to that for the as-fabricated condition. In addition, each of the solution treatments results in a rupture life which exceeds the 300 hour criterion. The super-transus excursion also results in approximately an order of magnitude increase in the minimum creep rate. Finally, all of the solution treatments result in a significant extension of the primary creep regime.

Table III. Effect of Solution Treatment Temperature on 650°C/172MPa Isothermal Creep

Condition	Time (hr)			300 hr	S.S. Creep Rate	Primary Creep (hrs)
	0.2%	0.4%	1.0%			
As-fab'd	1.4	5.4	28	No(147hrs)	3.1E-08	57
1025°C	3.0	12.4	63	Yes	1.6E-08	180
1050°C	8.7	31.1	179	Yes	1.2E-08	200
1075°C	8.5	41.0	290	Yes	1.2E-08	220
1125°C	22.5	87.5	*	Yes	5.9E-09	225

*Did not reach 1.0% creep strain before 300hr criterion was met

In an effort to understand the effect of microstructure on damage accumulation during creep, a neat sample which had been solution treated and direct aged (1025°C/2hr+28°C/min + 815°C/8hr/FC) was crept at 650°C/172MPa to a total creep strain of ~2.0%. The corresponding microstructure is shown in Figure 3. It can be noticed (Fig 3a) that the primary deformation mode appears to be by crack initiation at the interface between the "O" phase (at the rim of the primary α_2) and adjacent phase(s). Furthermore, there is little evidence of crack initiation at the lath "O"/B2 interfaces (Fig 3b). Therefore, one might deduce, that if the volume fraction of the primary α_2 phase was decreased (and hence the volume fraction of the rim "O" phase), and correspondingly, the volume fraction of the lath "O" phase was increased, that the creep resistance would increase. Figure 4 contains a plot of the time required to reach a creep strain of 0.4% versus the volume fraction of primary α_2 present in the microstructure. It is seen that as the volume fraction of primary α_2 decreases, the time to reach 0.4% creep strain steadily increases. Conversely, Figure 5 illustrates the effect of "O" phase content on time

Figure 3. Creep Damage Accumulation at 650°C/172MPa to 2.0% Creep Strain indicating (a) Crack Initiation at Interface of Rim "O" and Adjacent Phases and (b) No Cracking at lath "O"/B2 Interfaces.

Figure 4. Effect of Volume Fraction of Primary α_2 phase on Time Required to Reach 0.4% Creep Strain at 650°C/172MPa.

Figure 5. Effect of Volume Fraction of "O" Phase on Time Required to Reach 0.4% Creep Strain at 650°C/172MPa.

required to reach 0.4% creep strain. Here it is seen, that as the volume fraction of "O" phase increases, so does the creep resistance. It should be noted that in both instances, the volume fraction of B2 remains essentially constant, such that the increase in lath "O" is proportional to the decrease in α_2 . There are at least two possible explanations for this behavior. First, it has been previously demonstrated for $\alpha_2 + \beta$ alloys, Ti-25Al-10Nb-3V-1Mo and Ti-24Al-11Nb, that lath structures are stronger in creep than equiaxed structures (13-15). Furthermore, Banerjee et al (16) have demonstrated that the "O" phase is substantially stronger in creep resistance than the α_2 phase.

The effect of aging treatment and cooling rate on creep response is depicted in Table IV. Comparisons are made against the as-fabricated condition and the baseline heat treatment condition (1075°C/2hr + 28°C/min + 815°C/8hr/FC). It can be seen that all of the heat treatments resulted in improved creep resistance when compared to the as-fabricated condition. This is most likely the result of increased levels of "O" phase and corresponding decreases in α_2 . It can be noticed that the effect of aging treatment on creep response was rather minimal. Both the high and low temperature aging temperatures resulted in very similar times to 0.4% creep strain, steady-state creep rates, and primary creep lives. This was true despite that fact that the volume fractions of the various phases were changing, as well as, the scale of the lath microstructure. This observation can be explained in terms of competing effects. The low temperature aging treatment resulted in a much finer lath size which would tend to favor increased creep rates. However, the same aging treatment produced decreased levels of α_2 with corresponding increases in "O", both of which tend to result in decreased creep rates. Similarly for the high temperature age, the scale of the lath structure has increased, while the volume fraction of α_2 increases and the "O" phase decreases. The net result is that the creep performance remains essentially unchanged when compared to the baseline aging condition. The effect of cooling rate was more dramatic. It is noticed that reducing the cooling rate by an order of magnitude to 2.8°C/min results in a two-fold decrease in the time to 0.4% creep strain, although the steady state creep rate and primary creep life remain essentially unchanged. This result can be rationalized by noting that the slower cooling rate produced a lath structure similar in width to that observed for the faster cooling rate, but reduced in length, while the relative volume fractions of α_2 increased and "O" decreased.

Table IV. Effect of Aging Treatment and Cooling Rate on 650°C/172MPa Isothermal Creep

Condition	Time (hr)			300 hr Rupture Criterion?	S.S. Creep Rate	Primary Life (hr)
	0.2%	0.4%	1.0%			
As-fab'd	1.4	5.4	28	No(147hrs)	3.1E-08	57
Baseline	8.5	41.0	290	Yes	1.2E-08	220
Lo Temp Age ¹	9.4	36.8	214	Yes	6.8E-09	230
Hi Temp Age ²	6.9	36.8	226	Yes	8.2E-09	240
Slo Cool Rate ³	3.8	19.6	129	Yes	9.0E-09	230

11075°C/2hr+28°C/min+760°C/16hr/FC

21075°C/2hr+28°C/min+870°C/4hr/FC

31075°C/2hr+2.8°C/min+815°C/8hr/FC

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study has demonstrated the effects of post consolidation heat treatments on the longitudinal tensile and creep performance of a neat "orthorhombic" titanium aluminide composition, Ti-22Al-23Nb(a%). The heat treatments were chosen such that they might eventually be incorporated into the consolidation cycle for continuous fiber reinforced composites. It was found that this composition, much like conventional $\alpha+\beta$ titanium alloys can be heat treated to improved combinations of tensile and creep performance.

All of the sub-transus heat treatments resulted in an increase in UTS, YS, %El and modulus with respect to the as-fabricated condition, with the exception of the slower cooling rate which had slightly inferior UTS and YS values. The best balance of properties was produced by the β_{tr} -50°C (i.e. 1050°C) solution treatment. These increases were rationalized in terms of increases in "O" phase content, decreases in α_2 , and refinement in microstructural features. A super-transus solution treatment resulted in significant improvements in UTS, YS and modulus,

again compared to the as-fabricated condition, but with reduced ductility as a result of aligned α_2 or "O" platelet formation at or near prior beta grain boundaries.

The isothermal creep performance (650°C/172 MPa) provided by each of the heat treatments was also improved compared to the as-fabricated condition. The effect of solution treatment on time to reach 0.4% creep strain was correlated with volume fractions of α_2 and "O". It was found that increases in "O" and associated decreases in α_2 , increased creep performance. The best creep results were afforded by the super-transus solution treatment, $\beta_{tr}+25^\circ\text{C}$ (i.e. 1125°C), which provided for a 15x life extension to 0.4% creep strain. The effect of aging temperature on creep was found to be minimal over the range of temperatures examined (760-870°C). This was rationalized based upon competing effects of relative volume fractions of phases and "O" lath size. The effect of decreasing the cooling rate (between solution treatment and aging temperatures) by an order of magnitude, reduced the time to 0.4% creep strain by a factor of ~2, as a result of increased α_2 and decreased "O" volume fractions. While all of the heat treatments surpassed a 300 hour rupture criterion, none exceeded the 100 hour to 0.4% creep strain requirement (although the super-transus solution treatment resulted in >87 hours). This would suggest that alloy modification in combination with heat treatment may be required. In addition, the effects of the subject heat treatments on transverse properties, as well as, cyclic response are the focus of continuing studies. Finally, optimum heat treatment(s) must be applied to the fiber reinforced composite and evaluated for their effect on composite mechanical performance.

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